

PHYSICAL EDUCATION UNIFORMS: A SPECTRUM APPROACH

by

Nica D. Lampe

ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2631-0405

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6654414

A Project Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the
Requirements to Graduate with University Honors

The University Honors Program
California State University, Fullerton
May 2022

Approved by:

Dr. John Gleaves, Department of Kinesiology

Dr. Yuying Tsong, Director University Honors Program

Date:

5/10/2022

5/31/2022

Introduction

This Senior Honors Project shares the process of creating a spectrum of physical education uniforms. This spectrum includes a range of my own designs as well as the uniforms used in physical education classes today. This spectrum can be mix-and-matched to allow students to pick the garments they believe will best support their endeavors in the physical education classes ahead. Changing the uniforms is one of the many ways that willingness to participate in physical education classes could be increased. This project includes a literature review, the creation of a technical pack and physical mock-up garments, and the next steps to be taken in order to implement these designs into physical education classes.

A Literature Review of Physical Education Uniforms for Girls: Why We Should Rethink Physical Education Uniforms for Middle and High School Students

There is a pronounced difference in the participation rates of boys and girls in physical education classes. This difference is partially fueled by the lack of a desirable uniform that is comfortable and easy to wear for various shapes, sizes, preferences, and identities. The current uniform reflects the stereotype that boys come first in the realm of sports and physical activity, and girls' preferences and needs are disregarded. My research aims to fill the gap by designing a physical education uniform for female and gender-nonconforming students that will foster greater participation and willingness to enjoy physical education. By keeping girls in unisex uniforms intended for boys, we are not only taking away their potential to participate in physical activity but leaving a life-long dislike for physical activity that can have serious health consequences later in

life. By looking at the history of women's athletic wear, barriers to women in physical activity, and the experiences of girls in physical education classes, the themes of control, shame, and exploitation.

The History of Women's Athletic Wear

Private Athletic Wear and Social Sportswear Costumes

The history of the evolution of women's sportswear takes two distinctly different paths. One path follows the development of sportswear costumes worn during games played while intermingling with the opposite sex (Warner, 2006). This clothing closely followed the most current trends at the time. The other path follows the evolution of athletic wear worn to allow freedom of movement and limited restrictions in order to participate in segregated physical activity (Warner, 2006). Most often, there were no specific pieces of clothing marketed and sold for this purpose, so more accessible pieces were used instead. Women participated in physical activity secluded from the opposite sex (Warner, 2006). Therefore, they were not held to the social restrictions of dress and behavior that bound them to more restrictive and

less revealing garments. The clothing worn during social games closely followed the popular fashion of the time with minor alterations to make the costume more suitable for the game. Playing games allowed the sexes to intermingle and court, an opportunity not allowed for generations before them who had to be chaperoned for such occasions. The

most popular game in the 1850s was croquet, and special skirt elevators were attached to a lady's outer skirts to lift and keep them from dragging on the ground (Warner, 2006). Because the petticoat was on display, there was also an increase in the amount of delicate lace and detailed embroidery on this once private underlayer of clothing as it became more popular to have them show. The game of croquet was viewed as more of a match-making event rather than a competitive sport. During this time in history, women were expected to learn the games in the privacy of their home with the guidance of a trusted friend or brother and only participate in public once she had gained proficiency at it (Warner, 2006). Herein lies the value of having two distinct types of clothing for different activities. The athletic wear allowed for greater movement, making the private practice of skills much more accomplishable, and once the skill was improved, the sportswear costume would be worn to go out and show off the skills at a social event.

Divided Skirts for Ice Skating

Ice skating was another popular activity to intermingle with the opposite sex, and

as winter rolled in, it became too cold to play croquet. Ice skating took over as a popular place to meet and matchmake. Ice skating was the first activity in which serious alterations to the women's costume had to be made, representing it as the beginning of the evolution of women's sport-specific clothing or athletic wear (Warner, 2006). For the ice skating costume, an entirely new garment needed to be constructed to allow women to glide safely on the ice. Divided skirts were worn underneath

the outer skirts and sometimes even took the place of layered petticoats. This was the first point in the development of women's athletic wear that bloomers or divided skirts began to be worn and shown.

Shorter Hemlines for Tennis

Tennis was the next sport women became involved in around the 1880s that had a lasting impression on the look of women's athletic wear. Because the sport was not sex-segregated, women still wore the most popular fashions of the time (Warner, 2006).

As the game grew in competitiveness, the women's costumes evolved and changed to suit their needs. Gone was the movement restricting corset, trip hazard floor-length skirt, and fitted long sleeves (Warner, 2006). By removing garments and altering the lengths of the

skirt and top, women were allowed much more freedom of movement and became much more competitive in the

games. Altered menswear became the most popular choice as it gained popularity among colleges as

"tailor-mades" (Warner, 2006). This is the first point where we see women begin to take aspects from men's

clothing and alter them to suit their needs, but it is

certainly not the last. As borrowing aspects from menswear became more popular, the no waist style, which had been introduced at colleges a decade earlier, became popularized.

Modesty for Bathing Costumes

Bathing was the next most popular leisure sports activity that gained popularity by the 1890s. This posed a significant dilemma when selecting a bathing costume that would

maintain the appropriate level of societal modesty when wet but provide the freedom of movement and a lightweight feel for safety in the water. The bloomer costume made its

resurgence in popularity and set the standard for all bathing costumes that followed. Initially, it consisted of a baggy blouse-top dress cut to the mid-calf and gathered at the waist with a belt; underneath, trousers were worn that finished with a ruffle at the bottom hem, and an optional cape could be worn after swimming to provide warmth and additional coverage should the wet blouse top cling too closely to the body and become immodest (Warner, 2006).

Women in America who forwent the skirt over the bloomers were considered masculine, so most women kept the skirt layer on to avoid public scrutiny. The French-style bathing dress was the next hottest trend that followed a similar construction to the gymnastic suit that emerged around the same time (Warner, 2006). Because of their similarities, patterns were created to be altered for whichever the wearer needed to make. This costume showcased shorter

pants cut off at the knee, short sleeves, and an optional skirt (Warner, 2006). Because of the continued shortening of sleeves and hemlines, women were pressured to begin shaving their legs and armpits. Swimming corsets were also made to be worn under

the costumes to support the body and promote good posture (Warner, 2006). Tight lacing was not encouraged during this time as the corset was viewed more as a foundational garment, much like the bra is today. The evolution of the bathing costume is directly connected to modesty standards and gender expectations for women.

Bloomers for Bicycling

The bicycle bloomer grew out of the dress reform movement in America and reached its peak around the mid-1890s. The original bloomer costume carried the reputation of being widely hated, and women who wore them in public were ridiculed by society. This is because of where the bloomer had evolved from. Pantaloons for little girls were introduced as a companion piece to the skeleton suit for little boys (Warner, 2006). They were long and full pants that finished with a ruffle at the hem. They were worn under light dresses and stayed long even as the hemlines shortened over time. They were mainly worn during physical activity and playtime. Because it was never worn without a skirt, pantaloons took on a role as underwear (Warner, 2006). This adds context to why modest society hated bloomers so immediately and passionately.

The Rise and Fall of the Bloomer Costume

Women attending college were the first to wear the gymnastic suit outside of physical education classes. The older generations of professors immediately made it very clear that the gymnastic suit was only to be worn within the confines of their physical education classes. The popular design was a kilt skirt with a box pleat in the front, with

slimmer knickerbockers worn underneath or attached at the skirt yoke (Warner, 2006). Bloomer costumes were so publicly ridiculed and critiqued that as the bicycling craze began to fade, bloomers all but disappeared from the public eye aside from those immediately covered by a skirt after unmounting the bike. Here in history, we see a parallel to today's popularization of leggings. Within both their original rises to popularity, it was claimed that those only with acceptable figures would look appropriate wearing them according to public opinion.

Victorian Era Corsetry and Negative Outcomes for Women

The Victorian Era rushed in a resurgence of ever-larger petticoats and skirts along with the trend of corsetry we know today as tightlacing (Warner, 2006). Because corsets covered the entire midsection of the body from chest to hips, they hindered movement

exponentially. With an increased emphasis on a small waist; dieting, tightlacing, and padding were used but led to fainting spells and other adverse health consequences (Warner, 2006). This time period is where the negative connotation with corsetry began. The shift away from a foundational garment and towards a shaping garment made

modern women believe corsets were bad for women's health. With the rise of Muscular Christianity, the false connotation that sports and physical activity are mainly masculine activities was a widely pervasive opinion that segregated women from participating in sports (McCullough, 2007). As women stopped being physically active, clothing for the

activities was no longer necessary. During this time, very few women were permitted to pursue higher education and with that, physical education.

The Comeback of Physical Activity for Women

Following this time, physical fitness started to be widely recommended to girls as old as sixteen and included running, jumping, playing ball, etc.

The Turkish costume came to the forefront during this period, consisting of pantaloons or trousers and a blouse covering the shoulders and chest (Warner, 2006). Because of the lack of physical activity in the previous decade, it became apparent to doctors that movement was necessary for maintaining a healthy body. Calisthenics was introduced through magazines as a necessary part of a girls' education (Warner, 2006). Magazines played a vital role in the education of young girls at this time as

they typically did not attend a school. As more women began to pursue higher education, they began to enroll in the physical education classes that were a co-enrollment requirement to track health and well-being (McCullough, 2007). At this time, physical education classes were segregated by sex, allowing women to wear what was most comfortable and appropriate for the activities of the course, even if those clothes would be considered scandalous and revealing for everyday wear out in society. This new demand for women's activewear led to the rise in popularity of the bloomer costume, and later, the inception of the middy uniform.

Women's Involvement in the Olympics

The Olympics became the next station that put women's athletic wear trends and controversy in news headlines. Modesty was no longer the top priority as tighter and knit stretch fabrics like Lastex and nylon allowed records to be broken in more fitted suits

(Warner, 2006). Fabric and construction took precedence with an emphasis on faster times and better range of motion. Women's involvement in the Olympics was lacking due to many factors, including the focus on aesthetics over accomplishment, concerns from observers over the loss of femininity of the participating athletes, and Baron Pierre de Coubertin's strong aversion to having women participate in the Olympics at all (Warner, 2006). After World War 2, the styles of private gym wear and public sportswear

began to merge into one category as many wearers started to incorporate aspects of both styles to suit their needs.

Women's Uniforms for Physical Activity

The popularity of physical education grew the demand for clothes that allowed women to participate in physical activities. The first known women's uniforms for team sports in America came from the women's rowing team at Wellesley College, who took the initiative towards loose and comfortable tops. The design changed throughout the years, with some shifting focus more on comfort and

others focusing heavily on popular fashion. The blouse was very similar to the gymnastics costume, but the skirt was full in length since the sport was performed in front of male spectators (Warner, 2006). The outfitting of the long and full skirt calls back to the sporting costumes worn during social courting games among the opposite sex. In the beginning, singing and aesthetic beauty were requirements held above muscular strength and endurance (Warner, 2006). Intercollegiate competition was strictly discouraged by women's colleges. This did not stop the women on these teams from wanting to train to be competitive. As the mood shifted to valuing physicality, the girls

began wearing bloomers to row, and singing voice or visual aesthetics were no longer considerations for a spot on the team (Warner, 2006). After twenty years of uniform iterations, function won over fashion with only minor nods to cutting edge fashion and major emphasis on comfort. This shift is entirely due to the change in focus of the rowing team, from gentle rowing activities

that allowed the women to sing and look beautiful for the spectating audience to intense displays of strength and coordination among the whole team during races. As sports became more competitive and more women wanted to participate, the uniforms evolved to suit their needs rather than hold them back from competing at their best.

The Evolution of the Gym Suit

With the introduction of more physically demanding sports came the inception of the Gym Suit. Butterick patterned the gymnastic bloomer in 1893, and commercial

companies began to manufacture them as well (Warner, 2006). The skirt's end and the bloomer's rise led to an immediate decline in spectators at women's games, with some colleges requiring teams wearing bloomer uniforms to be spectated by women only. Uniforms up until this point were made of flannel or wool, super sweat-absorbent, and never washed (Warner, 2006). New designs were created to combat the tight waist and allow undergarments to be worn and cleaned. The cotton middy top replaced the sailor blouse, hiding the waist and being paired with bloomers and washed

(Warner, 2006). Women's college sportswear of the 1910s had a considerable influence on the streetwear fashions of the 1920s (Warner, 2006). In the 1930s, the final evolution of the bloomer and middy uniforms culminated in a shortened romper with elastic shorts falling at the thigh, fully washable, worn with a blouse underneath and an optional skirt (Warner, 2006). Mass manufacturing

of this uniform allowed its popularity to surge as it was looser, unadorned, and could be used by every school that wished their students to have them. These uniforms were used until the 1970s, when the shift to the current popular unisex physical education uniform began.

The Controlling of Women's Bodies

Popular at the time, the concepts of body shaping were taught in physical education classes and led to a rise in body surveillance, public shaming, and social critique (McCullough, 2007). As fewer restrictions were socially obligated on women, more freedoms in dress and self-expression came about. Sporting leagues implemented harsh restrictions on the style of dress, both on and off the field, policing the way women wore their hair and makeup, and even banning the wearing of shorts and pants altogether (McCullough, 2007). The implementation of uniforms soon followed without considering any input from the women who would be required to wear them. Control of women's bodies was a prevalent theme during this time. The culture of America brings along with it gendered expectations of how people should and should not act (Krane, 2001). These gendered expectations set out how masculine and feminine people should behave, and if they are not followed, that person is not socially accepted.

The Feminizing of Sport

Even before the passage of Title IX in 1972, many people in sports were opposed to the idea that a woman could play sports on an equal level of physicality as a man. Women who joined men's sports were accused of feminizing the sport, which caused a mass exodus of all men involved to avoid being labeled feminine (Cahn, 2015). A remarkable example of this shift in the gender of participants is cheerleading. As more women became educated, joined the paid labor force, and participated in reform movements, the athletic girl became a symbol of modern women in the early twentieth century (Cahn, 2015). The symbolism of the athletic girl in the modern feminist

movement led to more women becoming involved in sports, coaching, physical activity, and physical education. Physical educators still believed that physical education could damage the female reproductive system, promote sexuality, and blur gender differences between the sexes (Cahn, 2015). Because of these beliefs, physical activity was altered to avoid the masculine effects.

Profiting off of Women in Sports

During the 1970s, women's sports began to boom in popularity. Male-dominating sports leagues began to take an interest in taking control of women's collegiate leagues, viewing them only as a method of exploitation and profit (Cahn, 2015). The only period when women were publicly encouraged and socially accepted to participate in sports, and physical activity was when men could profit off them. This boom in popularity came from the spreading of the cultural and sexual revolution of the 1960s and 70s, which emphasized women's ability to seek bodily pleasure, physical freedom, and leisure time, giving many women an opportunity to participate freely in sports and physical activity (Cahn, 2015). With this emphasis, women had much more free time to spend focusing on themselves and being physically active. The continued trend grew the market for sporting equipment, clothing, and accessories and marketed to push more Americans to participate in sports, developing into a multimillion-dollar industry (Cahn, 2015). During this marketing push, brands recognized the unrealized profits to be made in this sector, and a shift away from the pink-it and shrink-it mentality began moving towards the specialization of women's athletic wear.

The Passage of Title IX and Long-Term Effects on Women's Collegiate Sports

Title IX allowed for great strides to be made toward gender equality, but there are some effects of its passage that did the exact opposite of what the bill intended. The National Collegiate Athletic Association (NCAA) was strongly opposed to the passage of Title IX and went as far as lobbying the Department of Health, Education, and Welfare, as well as Congress, to excuse athletic departments from following the regulations (Cahn, 2015). Professional athletic teams were encouraged to remain profitable by corporate demands to promote a sexy feminine image to stay relevant. The NCAA had failed in its attempts to block Title IX in the early 1980s, and then tried to take control of women's intercollegiate athletics. Because men's sports received more resources than women's sports, female athletes had no choice but to compete in male controlled sporting organizations whose decisions were influenced by corporations focused on profit, not equity (Cahn, 2015). The revolution of women's participation in sports continued after the passage of Title IX, which banned sex-based discrimination in education and allowed women to participate in physical education and sports on par with men.

The passage of Title IX followed with pressure being put on sports leagues and institutions to fix their gender inequalities by submitting lawsuits. Women's sports advocates shared similar agendas with the broader feminist movement that encouraged women to explore their sexuality (Cahn, 2015). Women's lives were being revolutionized by the dismantling of the rampant sexism and, as a product, improving women's condition of living. As a result of Title IX, most schools merged the separate women's and men's athletic departments and, in almost every case, named a man as department

head and all other administrative and coaching positions (Cahn, 2015). Although Title IX aimed to combat the gender inequalities rampant in physical education and coaching in schools, it backfired and allowed men to take over almost all of the positions once held by women. The cost of access to sporting opportunities and resources gives control over to men. In today's professional leagues, priority is given to teams that profit. Unless women's sports teams are willing to sacrifice their athleticism for sex appeal, their events will not receive financial support. Corporations pressure the women on their teams to trade in the baggy comfort of their college uniforms for the revealing, form fitting spandex uniforms (Cahn, 2015). The spandex uniforms are not always the best choice for many sports. In some cases, the spandex uniforms may hinder the athletes abilities to perform at their best. Big-time women's sports is a minor profit for multibillion-dollar corporations who are much more interested in commercializing the oversexualized sporting world, creating insecurities, and selling sports and fitness to ordinary women (Cahn, 2015). These companies capitalize on widespread obsessive anxieties women have felt about body weight and social pressure to maintain an ideal look they have handcrafted using photoshop and visual effects.

The Pressure to be a Feminine Woman in Sports

Many women who participate in sports tend to play up their feminine traits to avoid prejudice and are even required to keep up their feminine outward appearance both on and off the playing field in certain leagues or teams. Women who participate in traditionally masculine sports are often viewed as being more manly or even labeled as homosexual, solely based on the sport they choose to enjoy (Krane, 2001). This pressure

to act a certain way is not only demonstrated on the everyday woman but is applied tenfold to the athletic woman since the two terms are contradictory in the eyes of society. Just by participating in sports and physical activity, women are empowering themselves and others to debunk the stereotype that maintains sports are masculine and break down the walls to allow women to make their own choices about appearance and behavior.

One Step Forward, Three Steps Back

Today, sporting institutions and resources continue to be dominated by men. The world of women's sports still reflects generations of deeply inscribed sex roles and values hostile to women's participation and enjoyment of sports (Cahn, 2015). As the world continues to view sports as a masculine activity, women will continue to be pushed to the sidelines and discouraged from participating. On the flip side, women are permitted and encouraged or even pressured to take up physical fitness because commercial media consistently regulates their body's outward appearance and sexuality (Cahn, 2015). This constant pressure many women feel to always be perfect and maintain an ideal body by being physically fit is more harmful than it is helpful. Although many companies and healthcare professionals speak to the benefits of physical activity when combating the obesity epidemic, very few mention the adverse effects social media and popular opinion have on the everyday woman simply striving to be healthy. Sports should no longer be seen as having masculine qualities but as having human qualities (Cahn, 2015). Everyone is capable of participating in sports and physical activity for their own personal enjoyment. That is why the masculine connotation that sports still carry to this day will

remain an archaic decoration of the past, and it is long since time for that false connotation to be dropped.

Barriers to Women in Physical Fitness

Among the many barriers to women in physical activity and sports, the most significant barrier is clothing. Throughout history, there has been a constant push and pull between clothing that is designed to liberate women and clothing that is designed to oppress them. One particularly exclusive piece of a woman's outfit is the sports bra.

The Sports Bra

When not outright required, sports bras are strongly recommended not only for hygienic reasons but also for the comfort and safety of girls participating in physical education classes in middle and high school. Sports bras have been through an epic journey, from starting as functional athletic support garments and evolving into an eroticized fashion statement. The inception of the Jogbra began a movement towards the creation of athleticwear and equipment targeted directly at women. The binding of breasts for physical activity has been practiced for decades and is historically documented in Greek and Roman culture (Schultz, 2014). As the women's athletic wear sector became more lucrative, a shift began in advertising that moved away from function and comfort toward the sexualization of the female form. This movement also took great strides in trivializing women's athleticism and selling products based on insecurities. Popular media spread the image of selectively athletic bodies and popularized the trend of being slim and fit while minimizing body fat and visible bulky muscle. During this time, the sports

bra also evolved as a tool to show off a "properly shaped" female body and perpetuate fatphobic trends that held women to a higher and more selective standard of attractiveness (Schultz, 2014). These unrealistic expectations that marketing pushes at women can have damaging effects on mental health and body image. Cost also became a limiting factor for women and girls, with the average sports bra costing thirty dollars (Schultz, 2014). This high cost is especially prohibitive to young women and girls in middle and high school physical education programs. Sports bras evolved quickly from a tool that allowed women freedom of movement to a tool that oppressed women from wanting to participate in physical activity at all. This is a theme we can trace throughout women's history in sports.

Athletic Wear Trends and Dress Codes

Athletic wear treads the very fine line of being equally functional and fashionable. Athletes who can design or choose their own uniforms are equally pressured by the need to win as they are by the need to appear fashionable and relevant. Trends in women's tennis clothing dating back to when women first participated in events always reveal the lack of autonomy women had in selecting their own outfits (Schultz, 2014). Women's ability to participate was conditional on the appearance of their costume, which also, as a matter of fact, limited them to less vigorous play. As fashion trends shifted away from full coverage skirts and blouses, women who started to dress more provocatively on the court began to experience more popularity and attention, regardless of their physical ability or playing style. This established dress code also pushed back against women of different body types being able to participate. Those who deviated from what was

accepted were viewed unfavorably. Creating a dress code that does not alienate specific body shapes and types is an issue still dealt with today in women's sports and can also be seen in middle and high school dress codes.

Professional Uniforms

In the broad spectrum of clothing available for all people, sexism is abundant in the design of women's clothing. Men's uniforms for professional and collegiate sports afford them much greater flexibility than the regulations for women's uniforms (Lebel, 2021). Conventional women's athletic wear of today has been tailored to the idealized version of western femininity and body standards. This not only affects professional athletes. This clothing is also marketed to

everyday women who simply want to partake in physical activity. Athletic wear and uniforms have the power to impact confidence levels, attitudes toward sports and physical activity, mood, and even performance levels (Lebel, 2021). Being in a uniform that is comfortable for the wearer boosts

confidence and may lead to better performance. Women's uniform designs focus more on catering to the male gaze than on increasing performance or confidence (Lebel, 2021). We also see this in the marketing of women's athletic wear that sells an idealized version of the female form. This concept reiterates the idea that society prioritizes women's aesthetic appeal over their athletic ability.

Additional Barriers to Sports and Physical Activity

Women's barriers in physical fitness and sports spaces greatly diminish their ability to participate and stay physically active. These barriers are based on the long-standing social opinion that sports are defeminizing. Because of this notion, the entire realm of sports and physical fitness is designed to accommodate men yet puts up barriers to entry for women. Examples range from the lack of doors or partitions in the women's changing areas or showers, and the lack of a women's only space in the gym to accommodate those with religious or personal restrictions (Cortis, 2009). Another broader example of this occurrence is implementing uniform requirements for women who participate in team and league sports. Required uniforms are often regulated by men in positions of power at leagues and impose rules that many of the women on the team may view as unnecessary or not conducive to the high level of performance demanded of them (Cortis, 2009). For reasons, whether personal or religious, these uniforms and the regulations that are imposed against them restrict access to many women who wish to participate. These examples do not accommodate the visual privacy that many women prefer when participating in physical activity to reduce their self-consciousness about lack of skill, beauty, or even body image.

Mental Health Aspects of Uniforms

Common trends in women's uniforms may be causing damage to the female athlete both physically and mentally. Tight and revealing uniforms can force women to experience self-surveillance and dissatisfaction with their bodies than in less revealing uniforms, and body monitoring and anxiety occur more frequently in sports with a heavy

focus on body aesthetics than in sports without (Lauer et al., 2018). Tight uniforms are causing women in sports greater dissatisfaction with their own bodies due to comparisons both to other women on their team and also to the ideal female athletic body image promoted by brands. Women in more revealing uniforms are more likely to compare their bodies to their teammates' bodies and experience body dysmorphia or develop eating disorders when their uniform reveals skin or has cutouts (Lauer et al., 2018). Overall, tight and revealing uniforms harm a women's mental performance and take away from their ability to perform uninhibitedly by their uniform. Performance consequences and discontinuing the sport altogether are common side effects of the forced regulation of tight and revealing uniforms in women's sports (Lauer et al., 2018). This consequence is especially important when discussing middle and high school uniforms worn during physical education classes.

Girls in Physical Education Classes

Girls in physical education classes report all around dissatisfaction with the course. These classes are structured in a way that puts boys' interests and passions at the forefront of the curriculum. Activities that girls want to participate in are placed on the back burner or considered extra-curricular activities. These activities are not often considered sports and are typically stereotyped as girls' sports. The values of adolescent boys and adolescent girls regarding physical fitness differ significantly. Social norms have infected the ideologies of young girls to put them in a position of discomfort while participating in physical education classes.

Barriers in the Physical Education Classroom

There are many reasons why girls dislike required physical education classes. These reasons include forced competition, degrading evaluation, sexual harassment, and size-based harassment from peers and teachers (Van Daalen 2005). Forced performance, pressure to succeed, and expectations put girls in a vulnerable position that can lead to negative feelings towards physical activity that can last their entire lives.

Barriers for Physical Education Uniforms

Physical Education uniforms are a gender-specific barrier that affects all girls in physical education classes who are required to wear a uniform (Elliott and Hoyle, 2014). Schools are faced with two choices with the current uniform market: Implementing a unisex physical education uniform or dividing students and gendering their clothing. As it turns out, neither option presents a fair opportunity for girls to participate and enjoy class time alongside their peers. Examine the first option, gendered uniforms. This option, at first glance, seems to be an excellent solution to boost participation, but hyper-feminine

uniforms can contribute to social gender division in school and sports (Howard, 2021). By putting girls in girls' uniforms, there may be issues with the pressure put on young children to choose to be seen as either masculine or feminine. By putting girls in boy's uniforms, we perpetuate the societal misnomer that sports are typically a masculine activity. The second option involves putting girls in unisex uniforms, which appears to be the solution that most schools in the United States have adopted. On paper, this

sounds great, but when looking at the design of the uniform, it is not genuinely unisex, but a boys' uniform that has been decided will work for girls as well. The current most common uniform type, the unisex uniform, accentuates alterations in body shape and does not come with adequate sizing options. Unisex uniforms are, in actuality, boy's uniforms and show their greater dominance in the field. When women are forced to wear them, it signifies that they must give up their bodily autonomy and conform to the masculinity their sport demands to be viewed as an equal on the playing field. This again perpetuates the idea that sports are initially designed for boys and that if girls want to participate, they must shed their femininity and conform to stereotypes. Whether unisex or sex-specific, each uniform bears its own issues and detriments to girls' physical and mental health. Instead of uniform policies that aim to have law and order by policing women's and girl's bodies, schools should be implementing policies that are inclusive and flexible with an emphasis on freedom of choice and fairness. Physical Education uniforms do not address the needs of girls. They should address the requirements requested in areas of modesty, decency, and dignity, as well as comfort and confidence. Dislike for the uniform only increases with age, and religion is one of the lowest ranking barriers concerning the uniform (Elliott and Hoyle, 2014). This means that more than just those girls concerned with religious reasons dislike the uniform for being revealing, inappropriate, and unfashionable. Some schools or teams may choose to implement uniforms because they are a good economical choice, demand group discipline, foster harmony among wearers, and maintain a level of hygiene for participants (Harris et al., 1974). Because of these reasons, putting students in uniforms seems like the best decision

for unity and increased performance. Although uniforms may have benefits, the lack of choice in the current uniform causes additional issues. Uniforms are one of the components that can cause this great dislike girls are experiencing. Both tight and loose uniforms pose unique issues. A tight uniform can be viewed as sexual because of exposure of the breasts, buttock, thighs, and stomach while loose clothing can create a striptease effect when worn during play by revealing parts of the body that usually would not be exposed when standing upright and still (Laure et al., 2018). The unisex uniform suffers from both of these issues as the mens shape does not fit the body of women and girls. Because sports are primarily mental, women and girls cannot be expected to perform at their greatest when their uniforms are harming their mental performance and inhibiting their ability to play freely (McCullough, 2007). Whether it is attributed to a degendering experience by wearing boys' uniforms, harassment from peers for having the autonomy of choice over body hair, or the shame associated with sizing, many girls are losing the ability to participate in physical activity classes because they are not able to wear the clothing of their choice.

Discussion

The impact of clothing on women's participation and enjoyment of physical activity has been well recorded throughout history to the modern-day. The clothing evolved in a way that was greatly dependent not only on the needs of each activity but also depending on the audience. Because of this split in the evolution of women's athletic wear that came back together before the turn of the twenty-first century, a divide between comfort and visual aesthetics can still be seen in designs coming out today. The available

literature tells of the history of women's sports and how athletic wear evolved alongside the struggles of women to reach equity in the realm of sports. It is argued that although there have been great strides taken before and since the passage of Title IX, there is still much more work that has yet to be done to close the gap. The gaps present in current knowledge about physical education uniforms and, more broadly, women's athletic wear is whether it is possible to create garments that will fix the issues present today that have culminated over the decades it has taken for women to be fully present and participating freely in sports and physical activity. Future studies must be conducted to provide uniforms for the generations of tomorrow. Due to the immense breadth of historical evidence available that suggests there is still inequality and pressures that disallow women to participate and enjoy sports and physical activity fully, work must be done in areas of athletic wear design to minimize self-consciousness, marketing that does not aim to make women insecure to make sales, and uniforms that allow children and growing adults to participate in sports and physical activity as a human enjoyment, and not just as a masculine pastime.

Methods: Designing the Uniform

Mood Board

The first step in my process for designing the uniform after the historical research had been completed was gathering images to create a mood board. This research consisted of gathering historical photos, vintage clothing archives, catalogs, exploring media from different brands, and collecting photos from catwalks and streetwear. These images served as inspiration and helped guide me in the general direction of how I

wanted my designs to turn out. I wanted the fabrication of the range to include soft and breathable outer fabrics with moisture-wicking fabric for the innerwear pieces. An emphasis was also placed on choosing fabrics that are easy to care for to allow them to be taken home and laundered many times throughout their life cycle, hopefully lasting the student their entire time at that school. Color pallets are best designed by the school districts using each individual school's signature colors. I also wanted to include adjustable elements not only to provide a personalized fit for each student but also to have a preppy and elevated look. Vintage inspiration included athletic wear and sportswear worn from the 1800s to today. The bloomer costume, the gym suit, and the middy uniform served as great vintage inspiration for garments that were worn and applied in physical education classes throughout the decades I studied. Taking a mix-and-match approach in my designs will allow the wearers to pick the garments they feel provide them with the best personalized fit and comfort. Vintage pieces offered a range of styles from ultra-masculine to ultra-feminine, and with this information, I decided it would be best to design my range to have shapes that were neither masculine nor feminine. Additional coverage was also a key feature of many vintage outfits. Elements of vintage pieces included pleated coverage, adjustable features, color-blocking, and a focus on increased range of motion. It is also important to keep in mind the many restrictions that made athletic wear for women unattainable. In place of sports bras, some women used bathing suits as they were more accessible. There is currently a big push for designers and brands to offer more diversity. This diversity is not only in their product line-ups, but also in their models and brand representatives.

Key Items

This research led me to five key pieces for my range: a long sleeved top, full-length flared pants, a short-sleeved loose-fitting top with a built-in sports bra, a mid-length skirt with built-in shorts, and mid-length flared shorts. This range of key items is designed to not include the standard tee-shirt and knee-length mesh shorts that most schools have adopted, as those can be included in the mix-and-match spectrum students can choose from alongside my new designs. The collected photos were then used as inspiration as I designed alternate technical drawings for each of the key items in my range. I used Prete-A-Template to digitally draw my initial sketches, and Adobe Illustrator to digitally design my technical drawings. From those, I chose the final designs for my range. I designed a sample school logo based on California State University, Fullerton's logo and mascot, and also created a sample color pallet using the school colors, making sure to include the Pantones for the manufacturer.

Creating a Technical Pack

A technical pack is used to show the evolution of clothing designs from the initial concept to the final design. This shows valuable information for the manufacturer. In my technical pack, I have included original sketches, technical drawings, color options, annotations, measurements, and a bill of materials and hardware. The original sketches were copied over and text was added to explain the thought process when designing. Technical drawings of the alternates were added, along with the images that inspired them. The final key items were added as technical drawings, and back drawings were added. Details were then added to the technical drawings of the final key items to show

things like stitches, trim, and additional elements. The sketches are then annotated with all valuable information for the manufacturer. Information such as stitch lengths, trim pieces, collars, linings, and internal tags was added to the technical drawings. The back waistband tag was designed to have a place for the wearer's name to be added to the garment. The internal tag with fabric composition would also

include the brand name as well as the size denomination. This tag would be hidden away along an internal side seam in the garment. A materials key was added with color to the annotations to show what part of the garment was the main body and inner lining and what trims went where on the garment. Finally, a bill of materials and hardware was created to tell the manufacturer the important information about what fabrics should be

used, what colors they are, what trims are used, and what hardware elements are included, as well as the cost of each.

Creating Mock-Ups of the Uniform

The next step in my process was to make a physical mock-up. A mock-up is an initial trial of the construction of the entire garment using cheaper cotton muslin fabric. They help determine fit issues and better represent the look of the technical drawings.

Creating the Patterns

In order to take my technical drawings and bring them to life as physical mock-ups, I needed to design patterns. Seamly 2D was the software I used to create the pattern pieces. It allowed me to input body measurements and create the pattern pieces for my designs. My patterns included important body markers and seam allowances that varied depending on the location for maximum comfort. The patterns were then cut out and taped together to be used effectively.

Cutting and Preparing the Fabric

I began the mock-up process by cutting out my fabric and ironing it flat. The fabric was then cut for each pattern piece, and important information was transferred

from the pattern to the fabric. Sewing began with the raw edges of the fabric and then moved to putting the separate pieces together using a straight stitch.

Mock-Up One

After the first mock-up was completed, I tried it on to determine fit issues and reflected the necessary changes onto the pattern pieces for the next mock-up. The sports bra insert needed to be lengthened by six inches on the front and back pieces and the armpit hole needed to be slightly lowered. The top needed one inch removed

from each side seam under the armpit and tapered down to the waist. The skirt needed to be shortened by half an inch, so I increased the seam allowance at the bottom seam to one inch. The shorts needed two and a half inches added to the back sides and one inch added to the front waist.

Reflecting Alterations onto the Pattern Pieces

After I decided what alterations needed to be made based on mock-up one, I needed to fix my pattern pieces. To do this, I reflected each change by inch onto the pattern pieces.

Mock-Up Two

The second mock-up was then created following the same steps with the only difference being it was a truly completed garment with finished and pressed seams. The armpit hole of the sports bra insert was still too small and needed to be increased, and an elastic band should be added to the bust band as well as to be

attached to the top by the shoulder seams. The top needs the armpit hole increased as well. The skirt needs elastic in the waistband and a closure in the back as well as to be

attached to the shorts by running seams aligned with the triangle leg cutouts. The shorts need elastic around the thigh openings and waistband. I believe most of these changes are better implemented by the manufacturer, with only the armpit adjustments needing to be made to the pattern pieces. Overall, this experience of creating mock-ups allowed me to get a good idea of what my technical drawings would look like as physical garments and how they would work on the body while participating in physical activity.

Next Steps

The next steps I need to take with this project are continuing the patterning and mock-up stages with the long-sleeved top, the pants, and the shorts. After those have been created, opinion testing and interviews would be beneficial with the target demographics of middle and high school students. Then a meeting should be scheduled with a local school district and physical educators to discuss the implementation of the uniforms into physical education classes and also discuss tweaks that should be made, fabric options, and Pantone colors for each school in the district. The completed technical pack can then be sent to a manufacturer for samples. The fit may need to be altered and the sample returned to the manufacturer until it is correct. The final samples should then be brought to the school board and physical educators for approval. Finally, a handout can be created using the technical drawings in the school colors for incoming students to order from.

Acknowledgments

Thank you so much to Dr. John Gleaves for being an incredible resource and the greatest mentor to me during this process. Thank you to California State University, Fullerton Associated Students Inc. for sponsoring my research and awarding me with a grant that allowed me to create the physical mock-ups. Thank you to the California State University, Fullerton Honors Program for supporting my undergraduate journey and inspiring me to research something I am passionate about. This project has completely altered my career aspirations, and I am so grateful to have been given the opportunity to explore and discover my passion for athletic wear design. And finally, thank you so much to my mom who supported me throughout this entire project, from the initial idea all the way to the final presentation. I could not have done it without you.

References

- Adobe Inc. (2022). *Adobe Illustrator*. Retrieved from <https://www.adobe.com/products/illustrator/ipad.html>
- Crim, C. H. (2014). *Pattern making for kids' clothes: All you need to know about designing, adapting, and customizing sewing patterns for children's clothing*.
- Elliott, D., & Hoyle, K. (2014). An examination of barriers to physical education for Christian and Muslim girls attending comprehensive secondary schools in the UK. *European Physical Education Review*, 20(3), 349–366.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1356336X14534358>
- Harris, M. B., Ramsey, S., Sims, D., & Stevenson, M. (1974). Effects of Uniforms on Perceptions of Pictures of Athletes. *Perceptual and Motor Skills*, 39(1), 59–62.
<https://doi.org/10.2466/pms.1974.39.1.59>
- Howard, Tess. (2021). Why Impractical And Hyper-Feminised PE Kits Are Putting Girls OFF SPORT. The Telegraph, Telegraph Media Group.
<https://www.telegraph.co.uk/womens-sport/2021/09/01/impractical-hyper-feminised-pe-kits-putting-girls-sport/?fbclid=IwAR0gBfD2vetom9qKqv9eNWsDtwiAHfHC5NHVAuIVH3u1vY8vWMm19c3o1RU>.
- Klomsten, A. T., Marsh, H. W., & Skaalvik, E. M. (2005). Adolescents' Perceptions of Masculine and Feminine Values in Sport and Physical Education: A Study of Gender Differences. *Sex Roles*, 52(9), 625–636.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11199-005-3730-x>

Krane, V. (2001). We Can Be Athletic and Feminine, But Do We Want To? Challenging Hegemonic Femininity in Women's Sport. *Quest* (National Association for Kinesiology in Higher Education), 53(1), 115–133.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/00336297.2001.10491733>

Lauer, E. E., Fisher, R. A. Z. & L. A., Bejar, M. P., McCowan, T., Martin, S. B., & Vosloo, J. (2018). NCAA DII Female Student-Athletes' Perceptions of Their Sport Uniforms and Body Image. *Journal of Sport Behavior*, 41(1), 40–63.

Lebel, K. (2021). Competing with confidence: Why we need to bring women's sport uniforms into the 21st century. *The Conversation*, The Conversation US, Inc.

https://theconversation.com/competing-with-confidence-why-we-need-to-bring-womens-sport-uniforms-into-the-21st-century-171273?utm_source=facebook&utm_medium=bylinefacebookbutton&fbclid=IwAR1Y-ym7kCpOI01f3c7Ee4UJZ56WgToDknPSLqttkoOMUI0J-b5wPY6O7ME

Pret A Template Ciracao E Comercializacao De Software De Moda Ltda. (2022).

Pret-a-Template. Retrieved from <https://www.pretatemplate.com>

Schultz, J. (2014). 1. What shall we wear for tennis?. In *Qualifying times : Points of change in U.S. women's sport* (pp.149-166). University of Illinois Press.

<http://www.jstor.org/stable/10.5406/j.ctt5vk0cg>

Schultz, J. (2014). 6. A cultural history of the sports bra. In *Qualifying times : Points of change in U.S. women's sport* (pp.149-166). University of Illinois Press.

Retrieved August 26, 2021, from <http://www.jstor.org/stable/10.5406/j.ctt5vk0cg>

Seamly Systems (2022). *Seamly2D*. Retrieved from <https://seamly.net>

Seamly Systems (2022). *SeamlyMe*. Retrieved from <https://seamly.net>

Search Press. (2016). *A-Z of sewing: The ultimate guide for everyone from sewing beginners to experts*.

van Daalen, C. (2005). Girls' Experiences in Physical Education: Competition, Evaluation, & Degradation. *The Journal of School Nursing*, 21(2), 115–121.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/10598405050210020901>

Warner, P. C. (2006). *When the girls came out to play: The birth of american sportswear*.

University of Massachusetts Press